

Correlation between Sleep Quality and Metacognition among Young Adults: A Gender Perspective

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Sleep is an essential biological process that influences cognitive functioning and psychological well-being, especially during young adulthood (Tubbs et al., 2019). The present study examined the relationship between sleep quality and metacognition among young adults, with a particular focus on gender differences. The main objective was to explore whether variation in sleep quality is associated with differences in metacognitive belief and thinking patterns. The study followed a quantitative, non-experimental correlational research design. A total sample of 202 young adults (101 males & 101 females) aged 18-32 years participated in the research through purposive quota sampling. Sleep quality was assessed using the Pittsburgh Sleep Quality Index (PSQI), while metacognitive beliefs were measured using the Metacognitions Questionnaire-30 (MCQ-30) (Buysse et al., 1989; Wells & Cartwright-Hatton, 2004). Data were collected through self-administered online questionnaire and analyzed using statistical techniques to determine the relationship between variables. The results showed that the average PSQI score indicated generally poor sleep quality among participants. A significant positive correlation was found between sleep quality and metacognitive beliefs, suggesting that higher level of maladaptive metacognition is associated with poorer sleep. When gender differences were examined, the relationship was significant among males but not significant among females. In conclusion, the findings suggest that metacognitive beliefs are related to sleep quality in young adults, particularly among males. These results highlight the potential importance of addressing maladaptive metacognitive patterns when developing strategies to improve sleep health in young adult populations.

Keywords: Sleep quality, metacognition, young adults, PSQI, MCQ-30, gender correlation

Sleep plays a vital role in maintaining physical health, emotional regulation, and cognitive functioning (Tubbs et al., 2019). Sleep quality refers to an individual's overall satisfaction with their sleep experience, including aspects such as sleep duration, sleep latency, sleep disturbances, and daytime functioning (Buysse, 2014; Nelson et al., 2022). Poor sleep quality has been associated with difficulties in attention, memory, emotional regulation, and decision-making (Rao et al., 2020; Verma et al., 2025). Among young adults, lifestyle factors such as academic pressure, increased exposure to screen, and irregular schedules often contribute to disturbed sleep patterns. As a result, sleep problems have been increasingly common in young adults and may significantly affect psychological functioning (Nelson et al., 2022).

Metacognition refers to the awareness and regulation of one's own thinking processes. It involves the ability to monitor, evaluate, and control cognitive activities such as learning, memory, and problem-solving (Flavell, 1979; Nelson & Narens, 1990). Metacognitive

processes play a critical role in shaping how individuals interpret their thoughts, regulate emotions, and respond to stressors. Dysfunctions in metacognitive regulation have been linked to maladaptive psychological outcomes, including anxiety, rumination, and stress (Wells & Cartwright-Hatton, 2004; Spada et al., 2008; Nordahl et al., 2022; Zamani et al., 2021). Since both sleep and cognitive regulation play important roles in psychological well-being, understanding the relationship between sleep quality and metacognition may provide important insights into cognitive functioning and mental health among young adults. Additionally, gender differences in sleep patterns and cognitive styles have been reported in earlier studies, making it important to explore whether these factors influence the relationship between sleep quality and metacognitive process (Flavell, 1979; Nelson & Narens, 1990).

Review of Literature

Research examining sleep quality has consistently shown that sleep disturbances are widespread among young adults, particularly within student populations. In India, several investigations have reported a high prevalence of poor sleep quality among medical students and community samples (Manzar et al., 2015; Verma et al., 2025; Yogesh et al., 2025). Academic demands, irregular daily routines, and lifestyle habits appear to play a central role in shaping sleep patterns in this group. Empirical studies have shown that a large proportion of medical student's report PSQI scores above the clinical threshold, indicating compromised sleep quality (Manzar et al., 2015). Poor sleep among students is frequently linked with increased psychological distress, including symptoms of anxiety, depression, and stress (Rao et al., 2020; Shivasakthimani et al., 2025). In particular, prolonged sleep latency-difficulty initiating sleep has been identified as an important factor associated with

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emotional difficulties (Manzar et al., 2015). Community-based investigations in India have also revealed meaningful relationships between sleep disturbances and mental health outcomes, demonstrating that individuals experiencing depressive symptoms often report poorer sleep quality (Shivasakthimani et al., 2025). The COVID-19 pandemic further highlighted the vulnerability of sleep patterns within the population, with surveys indicating a noticeable deterioration in subjective sleep quality during periods of lockdown and social disruption. Lifestyle variables such as physical activity have also been identified as important determinants of sleep health (Kanchan et al., 2020). Research conducted among medical students suggests that individuals engaging in moderate to high levels of physical activity report better sleep quality than those who maintain sedentary lifestyles (Yogesh et al., 2025). In addition to examining prevalence and determinants of sleep disturbances (Verma et al., 2025; Yogesh et al., 2025) validation studies conducted with Indian participants have confirmed that the Pittsburgh Sleep Quality Index is a reliable and valid tool for assessing sleep quality among young adults. International findings largely mirror these patterns. Large-scale epidemiological studies and meta-analyses conducted across multiple regions have demonstrated that sleep problems are not confined to a single cultural or geographic context but represent a global public health concern (Shivashaktimani et al., 2025). Studies conducted in countries such as China, Germany, and the United States have documented substantial proportions of adults reporting poor sleep quality. These investigations also identify several social and psychological contributors, including socioeconomic status, educational attainment, employment conditions, and psychological distress (Chen et al., 2024; Hinz et al., 2017; Buysse et al., 2008). Research conducted among athletes has additionally shown that while many individuals maintain adequate sleep duration, difficulties related to sleep onset and perceived sleep quality can still influence overall sleep health (Halsen et al., 2021). Other community studies have explored the relationship between different subjective sleep measures and found that various tools assess distinct dimensions of sleepwake functioning. Collectively, these findings highlight the complex and multifactorial nature of sleep quality, which is shaped by biological, psychological, and environmental influences (Rao et al., 2020).

Alongside the growing body of sleep research, extensive attention has been devoted to understanding metacognition and its role in psychological functioning. Metacognition refers to the set of beliefs and processes through which individuals monitor, interpret, and regulate their own thinking. These beliefs influence how individuals respond to intrusive thoughts, worry, and emotional challenges (Wells & Cartwright-Hatton, 2004). In the Indian research context, studies examining metacognition have often focused on clinical populations, revealing that maladaptive metacognitive beliefs are strongly associated with various psychological disorders. Individuals experiencing depression, suicidal behavior, anxiety disorders, or obsessive-compulsive symptoms tend to demonstrate higher levels of dysfunctional metacognitive beliefs when compared with healthy individuals (Roy et al., 2024; Sharma et al., 2022; Vishwanathan et al., 2022; Anand & Sharma, 2016). In particular, beliefs related to the perceived uncontrollability and danger of thoughts, as well as the need to control thinking processes, appear to be central features of psychological distress (Spada et al., 2008). Research involving anxiety disorders has also revealed differences in cognitive functioning and metacognitive awareness when

compared with non-clinical groups. These findings suggest that maladaptive metacognitive patterns may contribute to both the development and maintenance of emotional difficulties (Vishwanathan et al., 2022). Intervention-based research further supports this perspective, with studies demonstrating that Metacognitive Therapy can lead to meaningful reductions in symptoms of depression, anxiety, rumination, and worry by directly targeting dysfunctional metacognitive beliefs (Sharma et al., 2022). While some investigations have explored the relationship between metacognition and physiological factors such as body mass index, the results suggest that these relationships tend to be relatively weak, indicating that psychological factors may play a more prominent role in shaping metacognitive beliefs (Dash et al., 2025). Research conducted in international contexts provides strong psychometric evidence supporting the measurement and theoretical structure of metacognition (Typaldou et al., 2010; Spada et al., 2008; Nordahl et al., 2022). Studies validating the Metacognitions Questionnaire-30 across diverse populations consistently confirm its five-factor structure, which includes cognitive confidence, positive beliefs about worry, negative beliefs regarding uncontrollability and danger, the need to control thoughts, and cognitive self-consciousness (Typaldou et al., 2010; Spada et al., 2008). Advanced statistical techniques such as network analysis and structural equation modeling have further illustrated that certain metacognitive domains occupy central positions within the broader cognitive system (Nordahl et al., 2022). In particular, the perceived need to control thoughts and negative beliefs about worry appear to function as key mechanisms connecting various aspects of metacognitive functioning (Nordahl et al., 2022). These domains are also strongly associated with emotional disorders such as anxiety and depression (Zamani et al., 2021). Overall, the existing literature suggests that metacognition is a crucial cognitive process influencing emotional regulation, vulnerability to psychopathology, and individuals' responses to internal experiences (Fisher et al., 2016).

In recent years, researchers have increasingly begun to examine the possible links between sleep quality and metacognitive functioning. Although this area of study remains relatively limited, emerging evidence suggests that sleep and metacognition may influence each other in important ways. Experimental research on sleep deprivation has demonstrated that insufficient sleep can impair cognitive performance and affect individuals' ability to accurately evaluate their own performance, thereby influencing metacognitive judgments (Sundelin et al., 2025). When individuals experience sleep loss, their awareness of cognitive performance may become less precise, which may lead to distorted evaluations of their abilities (Sundelin et al., 2025). Observational research has also highlighted associations between sleep patterns and metacognitive processes. For example, studies examining lifestyle behaviors have found that individuals reporting poor sleep quality often demonstrate higher levels of metacognitive worry and reduced cognitive regulation (Gooderham & Handy, 2025). Large-scale survey research has further indicated that insomnia symptoms and irregular sleep schedules are associated with poorer self-perceptions of cognitive functioning. These findings suggest that disturbances in sleep may affect how individuals perceive and regulate their own thinking processes (Nielson et al., 2023). Additional research using mediation models has provided further insight into these relationships by demonstrating that maladaptive cognitive strategies used to manage

intrusive thoughts about sleep may explain the link between metacognitive functioning and subjective sleep quality (Socci et al., 2023). Individuals who experience difficulties in regulating thoughts may rely on dysfunctional thought-control strategies, which in turn contribute to greater sleep disturbances (Socci et al., 2023). Structural equation modeling studies have also revealed that personality traits such as neuroticism may influence sleep quality indirectly through metacognitive beliefs and emotional regulation strategies. These findings indicate that cognitive and emotional processes may act as mechanisms connecting personality characteristics with sleep outcomes (Zamani et al., 2021). Taken together, the available evidence suggests that the relationship between sleep quality and metacognition may be bidirectional: poor sleep can impair cognitive self-monitoring, while maladaptive metacognitive beliefs may contribute to the persistence of sleep difficulties. Despite the growing interest in this area, an important gap in the literature remains the limited exploration of gender differences within the sleep-metacognition relationship. Although several studies include both male and female participants, gender-specific analyses are rarely conducted. This is noteworthy because previous research suggests that sleep patterns, emotional regulation strategies, and cognitive styles may differ across genders. Consequently, there is a clear need for further research that examines the relationship between sleep quality and metacognitive beliefs while taking gender differences into account.

Rationale

The relationship between sleep quality and metacognition is grounded in the Self-Regulatory Executive Function (S-REF) model. This model points those maladaptive metacognitive beliefs. Such as perceived uncontrollability of worry or excessive cognitive self-consciousness, trigger a "Cognitive Attentional Syndrome" that prevents the mental de-escalation necessary for sleep onset. For young adults, high scores in domains like Negative Beliefs about Worry and Need to Control Thoughts have been consistently linked to increased Sleep Latency and poorer Subjective Sleep Quality. (Buysse et al., 2014).

Furthermore, a gender perspective is essential to this inquiry, as epidemiological data indicate significant disparities in both sleep architecture and metacognitive styles between men and women. Studies suggest that women often report higher levels of ruminative thinking and negative metacognitive beliefs, which may correlate with the higher prevalence of insomnia reported in female populations (Nelson et al., 2022). Conversely, young adult men may experience different metacognitive pressures, such as lower Cognitive Confidence, which could manifest in distinct patterns of sleep fragmentation or daytime dysfunction.

Despite the established links between thought and sleep, there is a scarcity of research that explicitly explores how their variables interact through the lens of gender in the Indian young adult context. Investigating the correlation between Sleep Quality and Metacognition from a gendered standpoint is therefore vital. Such research provides a more nuanced understanding of there the gender-specific metacognitive interventions could serve as a viable pathway for improving sleep health in young adults.

Method

Participants

The present study adopted a quantitative, non-experimental, cross-

sectional correlation research design to examine relationship between sleep quality and metacognition among young adults, with a particular focus on gender relation. The sample consisted of 202 participants (101 males & 101 females) aged between 18 and 32 years, selected using purposive quota sampling, with inclusion criteria requiring participants to be able to read, write, and understand English.

The study was guided by null hypotheses stating that there would be no significant correlation bet sleep quality and metacognition overall, within male and female groups, and across five subdomains of metacognition (cognitive confidence, positive beliefs about worry, cognitive self-consciousness, negative beliefs about uncontrollability & danger, & beliefs about the need to control thoughts) for each gender.

Measure

Data was collected using standardized self-report questionnaires administered through an online survey format. Sleep quality was assessed using the Pittsburgh Sleep Quality Index (Buysse et al., 1989) while metacognitive processes were measured using the Metacognition Questionnaire-30 (Wells & Cartwright-Hatton, 2004).

Statistical Analysis

Statistical analysis involved the use of Pearson's correlation to determine the relationship between sleep quality and metacognition, including separate analyses for males and females as well as across metacognitive subdomains. Ethical considerations, including informed consent, voluntary participation, confidentiality, and the right to withdraw, were maintained throughout the research process.

Results

Table 1

Correlation between Sleep Quality and Metacognition (Total)

Variable	PSQI	MCQ
PSQI	-	0.25**
MCQ	0.25**	-

Note. $r=0.25^{**}, p<0.01$

H01: There will be no significant correlation between Sleep Quality and Metacognition among young adults

As shown in Table 1 a significant positive correlation ($r=0.25, p<.01$) was found. Hence *H01* is rejected.

Higher dysfunctional metacognitive beliefs are associated with poor sleep quality. This finding supports mediation model reported by Socci et al. (2023) where maladaptive metacognitive belief predicted higher PSQI scores. It also aligns with Nielson et al. (2023) who reported insomnia symptoms predicting poor subjective cognitive functioning.

The correlation strength is moderate, suggesting metacognition is an important predictor of sleep quality. But might not be the only predictor.

Table 2

Correlation between Sleep Quality and Metacognition (Total)

Variable	PSQI	MCQ
PSQI	-	0.09
MCQ	0.09	-

Note. $r=0.09, p>0.05$

H02: There will be no significant correlation between Sleep Quality and Metacognition among young females.

As shown in Table 2 the correlation is weak and non-significant. There for *H02* is retained.

Despite females reporting slightly poorer sleep quality, their metacognitive beliefs were not significantly associated with PSQI scores. This may indicate that other variable mediate sleep disturbance among females rather than metacognitive beliefs directly.

Table 3

Correlation between Sleep Quality & Metacognition (Males)

Variable	PSQI	MCQ
PSQI	-	0.09
MCQ	0.09	-

Note. $r = 0.38^{**}$, $p < 0.01$

H03: There will be no significant correlation between Sleep Quality and Metacognition among young males.

As shown in Table 3 a strong and significant positive correlation was found. Hence *H03* is rejected.

Among males, higher maladaptive cognitive beliefs are strongly associated with poor sleep quality. This supports the S-REF model, suggesting that worry about thoughts, uncontrollability and danger belief, and cognitive monitoring may interfere with sleep quality.

This also align with Gooderham and Handy (2025), who reported poor sleep predicting higher metacognitive worry.

Table 4

Correlation between 5 Domains of MCQ & Sleep Quality (Females)

Subscale	r with PSQI	p with PSQI
Cognitive Confidence	0.11	0.27
Positive Beliefs about Worry	0.05	0.59
Cognitive Self-Consciousness	-0.6	0.57
Uncontrollability and Danger	0.16	0.12
Need to Control Thoughts	0.06	0.55

H04: There is no Significant Correlation between 5 domains of Metacognition and Sleep Quality in young females.

As shown in Table 4 no Domain of Metacognition show significant association with Sleep quality, Hence *H04* is retained.

Table 5

Correlation between 5 Domains of MCQ & Sleep Quality (Males)

Subscale	r with PSQI	p with PSQI
Cognitive Confidence	0.3**	0.002
Positive Beliefs about Worry	0.25*	0.01
Cognitive Self-Consciousness	0.13	0.21
Uncontrollability and Danger	0.54**	<0.001
Need to Control Thoughts	0.36**	0.00

H05: There is no Significant Correlation between 5 domains of Metacognition and Sleep Quality in young males.

As shown in Table 5 Cognitive Confidence, Uncontrollability and Danger belief, need to Control Thoughts show strong correlation ($p > 0.01$) and Positive beliefs about worry show moderate correlation ($p > 0.05$) meanwhile Cognitive Self-Consciousness is not associated with Sleep Quality hence *H05* is Partially Rejected. This finding is

highly consistent with Wells and Mathews (1996) who emphasized uncontrollability beliefs as central to Cognitive Attentional Syndrome (CAS). The 'Need to Control Thoughts' domain also showed strong correlation supporting network analysis finding by Nordahl et al. (2022) where the Domain emerged as the most central metacognitive node.

The strongest predictor was Uncontrollability and Danger of Worry indicating that such belief significantly worsens sleep Quality.

Discussion

The study confirms a gender-differentiated relationship between sleep quality and metacognition, finding overall poor sleep quality is moderately associated with maladaptive metacognitive beliefs, which is significant and stronger in males, but no significant association was observed in females. These findings are in line with existing research indicating that sleep disturbance are linked with impairments in cognitive and metacognitive functioning (Nielson et al., 2023; Sundelin et al., 2025). Hence, the results support the theoretical assumptions of the Self-Regulatory Executive Functions (S-REF) Model, which proposes that maladaptive metacognitive beliefs contribute to heightened cognitive arousal and the maintenance of disturbed sleep (wells & Cartwright-Hatton, 2004; Spada et al., 2008).

The observed gender disparity suggests that the relationship between metacognition and sleep disturbance may operate differently across genders, possibly influenced by contextual, behavioral, and lifestyle factors (Rao et al., 2020; Shivsakhthimani et al., 2025) the stronger association between PSQI and MCQ scores among males indicates the sleep quality may play a more direct role in shaping metacognitive beliefs in the males. This is in line with the evidence showing the maladaptive cognitive strategies can influence sleep outcomes (Socci et al., 2023). Consequently, interventions such as Metacognitive therapy may be particularly beneficial in improving sleep health among males (Sharma et al., 2022). In contrast, the lack of significant association among females suggests that the sleep disturbances in this group may be influenced by a broader range of factors beyond maladaptive metacognitive beliefs alone, including emotional, biological, environmental and psychosocial influences,

Conclusion

The findings of this study indicate that young adults in the sample generally demonstrate poor average sleep quality. A significant positive relationship was observed between sleep disturbances and maladaptive metacognitive beliefs overall. However, this association was not statistically significant among female participants. Among males, the domain "Uncontrollability and Danger of Worry" emerged as the most influential metacognitive factor. These results suggest that metacognitive beliefs play an important role in sleep quality, particularly among young adult males

Limitations of the Study

Several limitations should be considered while interpreting the findings of this study. The cross-sectional design restricts the ability to establish causal relationships between sleep quality and metacognition. The use of self-report measures such as PSQI and

MCQ-30 may introduce response bias. The use of quota purposive sampling limits generalizability of the findings to broader populations. Additionally, potential confounding variables such as stress levels, caffeine consumption, and screen exposure were not controlled and biological factors such as hormonal changes and menstrual cycle variations among female participants were not assessed.

Future and Implications of the Study

Future research should consider longitudinal designs to better understand the direction and development of the relationship between sleep quality and metacognition over time. Gender-specific intervention studies, particularly those using Metacognitive Therapy, may provide useful insights into improving sleep outcomes. Researchers may also benefit from including objective sleep measures to complement self-report assessments. Also, exploring emotional regulation as potential mediating factor, especially among females, could provide a deeper understanding of the mechanisms linking cognitive processes and sleep quality.

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